

USE OF VANADOUS SULPHATE AS A REDUCING AGENT. PART V. ACTION OF VANADOUS SULPHATE UPON ORGANIC COMPOUNDS.

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Some organic nitro compounds, such as, nitrobenzene, dinitrobenzene, *p*-nitroaniline, and picric acid and two organic dyes : indigo and methylene blue have been estimated by reducing the nitro group in the former cases with vanadous sulphate. A known weight of the nitro compound was treated with an excess of vanadous sulphate and after boiling for some time under a reflux in a current of carbon dioxide, the mixture was cooled and the excess of V⁺⁺ solution was titrated with iron alum using sulphocyanide as indicator.

The powerful reducing action of vanadous salts is not confined to inorganic substances alone. A large number of organic substances belonging to both aliphatic and aromatic series are quantitatively reduced by bivalent vanadium salts. In these reactions, the reduction is more powerful and becomes complete much sooner at low acidities than at larger hydrogen ion concentration. So in many cases, in order to lower the acid concentration, Rochelle salt or sodium tartrate is added to the solution. Following pages contain an account of the estimation of some of these compounds.

Estimation of Nitro Compounds.

Reduction with Titanous Chloride.—The method described in this paper consists in the reduction of the nitro group with an excess of vanadous sulphate, followed by the determination of the excess with iron alum or any other suitable reagent. The reaction taking place may be represented by the equation,

In the reduction of the nitro group by Knecht-Hibbert method with titanous chloride it has been pointed out by Callan and Henderson (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1920, 39, 86r) that although in many cases it gives excellent results, yet for certain substances *e.g.*, *o*-nitroanisole, α -mononitronaphthalene, etc. the method gives low results. This is attributed to the titanous chloride solution acting not only as a reducing agent but also as a chlorinating agent, simultaneously liberating hydrogen by substitution which, in addition, acts as a reducing agent. If, however, titanous sulphate is used, in place of titanous chloride, with these substances under similar conditions, correct results are obtained.

Reduction with Stannous Chloride.—One serious defect of this method is that chlorinated amino compounds are formed as readily during reduction with this substance as with titanous chloride, and consequently low results are obtained. Nitro compounds which are not chlorinated may be estimated by stannous chloride method as modified by Young and Swain (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1897, 19, 812) with a fair degree of accuracy.

Reduction with Vanadous Sulphate.—With vanadous sulphate which has for the first time been employed for the estimation of nitro group in organic compounds, no question of chlorination comes in. The reduction takes place in the presence of sulphuric acid and the results are obtained which are as accurate as with titanous sulphate. The method has been successfully used for the estimation of a number of nitro compounds, *e.g.*, nitrobenzene, nitroaniline, etc. A known weight of the nitro compound is treated with a large excess of V^{III} salt and after boiling for some minutes under a reflux in a current of carbon dioxide, the mixture is cooled and the excess of V^{III} salt is titrated with iron alum, using sulphocyanide as indicator. When a nitro compound which is easily volatile or volatile with steam, heating must be done under reflux, otherwise low results due to the loss of the nitro compound by volatilisation may be obtained (Callan and Henderson, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1922, 41, 158r.). In dealing with such substances, the reduction is carried out in a flask fitted with a short ground-in water condenser, a stream of carbon dioxide being supplied by a narrow glass tube passing down through the inner tube of the condenser to within a few centimetres of the surface of the liquid. Nitro compounds which are insoluble in water or in acids (*e.g.* nitrobenzene) is to be sulphonated with sulphuric acid, while nitro compounds which, like dinitrobenzene, are neither soluble in water nor easy to sulphonate may be dissolved in alcohol and added slowly to the hot solution of vanadous sulphate contained in a flask through which a current of carbon dioxide is maintained. For accurate estimations, care must be taken to use a large excess of vanadous sulphate, to boil the solution with the reducing agent and to maintain a current of carbon dioxide during the entire estimation. Reduction becomes complete only when these precautions are carefully observed.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Estimation of Nitrobenzene.—0.5023 G. of chemically pure redistilled (b.p. 208°) nitrobenzene was sulphonated by heating with 20 c.c. of fuming sulphuric acid on a water-bath for two hours and the solution was made up to 250 c.c. A measured volume of this solution was run to an

excess of vanadous sulphate and after boiling for some minutes in a current of carbon dioxide, the contents were cooled and the excess of vanadous sulphate titrated back with iron alum. In another series of experiments, instead of sulphonating, 0.3906 g. of nitrobenzene was dissolved in alcohol and the solution made up to 250 c.c. The reduction was effected by boiling an aliquot part under reflux with excess of vanadous sulphate.

TABLE I.

$$V^{++}\text{soln.} = 0.2N. \quad Fe^{+++}\text{soln.} = 0.1N.$$

$$1 \text{ C.c. of } 0.1N \cdot V^{++}\text{soln.} = \frac{C_6H_5NO_2}{6 \times 10^4} = 0.00205 \text{ g. } C_6H_5NO_2.$$

Nitrobenzene taken.	V-soln. added.	Fe-soln. reqd.	Nitrobenzene found.	Remarks.
10 c.c.* (0.020092g)	10 c.c.	10.25 c.c.	99.44%	After sulphonation.
10 "	12	14.2	100.0	
10 "	15	20.25	99.4	
25 (0.05023)	20	15.6	99.59	
25 "	20	15.55	99.78	
10 (0.015624)	10	12.4	99.72	
10 "	10	12.4	99.72	
20 (0.031248)	20	24.8	99.70	Nitrobenzene dissolved in alcohol.
25 (0.03906)	20	20.95	99.99	
25 "	20	21.0	99.72	

* 10 c.c. contained 0.020092 g.

Estimation of Dinitrobenzene.—0.3374 G. of *m*-dinitrobenzene which was purified by recrystallisation from alcohol, was dissolved in alcohol and the solution made up to 250 c.c. A known volume of vanadous sulphate solution was measured into a conical flask, sulphuric acid was added, carbon dioxide passed over and a known volume of dinitrobenzene

solution run in. The mixture was boiled, allowed to cool and then titrated back with iron alum.

TABLE II.

V^{++} soln. = 0.2N. Fe^{+++} soln. = 0.1N.

$$1 \text{ C.c. of } 0.1N \text{ } V^{++} \text{ soln.} = \frac{C_6H_4(NO_2)_2}{12 \times 10^4} = 0.0014 \text{ g. } C_6H_4(NO_2)_2.$$

Dinitrobenzene taken.	V-soln. added.	Fe-soln. reqd.	Dinitrobenzene found.
10 c.c.*	12.5 c.c.	15.4 c.c.	99.60%
10	15.0	20.45	99.04
10	15.0	20.4	99.60

* 10 c.c. contained 0.013496 g.

Estimation of p-Nitroaniline.—The substance was purified by crystallisation several times from alcohol and drying at 100°. 0.5405 G. of the pure product (m.p. 147°) were dissolved in sulphuric acid and made up to 250 c.c. with water. A measured volume of this solution was reduced with an excess of vanadous sulphate in the usual way and the excess titrated with iron alum.

TABLE III.

V^{++} soln. = 0.202N. Fe^{+++} soln. = 0.1N.

$$1 \text{ C.c. of } 0.1N \text{ } V^{++} \text{ soln.} = \frac{C_6H_4NH_2NO_2}{6 \times 10^4} = 0.0023 \text{ g. } C_6H_4NO_2NH_2$$

Nitroaniline taken.	V-soln. added.	Fe-soln. reqd.	p-Nitroaniline found
10 c.c.*	10 c.c.	10.8 c.c.	100.0%
10	10.1	11.0	100.0
25	20.0	16.75	99.77
25	20.0	16.7	99.97

* 10 c.c. contained 0.02162 g.

Estimation of Picric Acid.—Picric acid (0.2928 g.) recrystallised several times from alcohol and having a melting point of 122.5° was dissolved in water and the solution made up to 250 c.c. A measured volume of vanadous sulphate was added to a known volume of this solution acidified with sulphuric acid, boiled for 10 to 15 minutes in a current of carbon dioxide and after cooling the excess of vanadous sulphate, titrated with iron alum.

TABLE IV.

$$V^{++} \text{ soln.} = 1.48 N/10. \quad Fe^{+++} \text{ soln.} = 0.1 N.$$

$$1 \text{ C.c. of } 0.1 N V^{++} \text{ soln.} = \frac{C_6H_5OH(NO_2)_2}{18 \times 10^4} = 0.001272 \text{ g. picric acid.}$$

Picric acid taken.	V-soln. added.	Fe-soln. reqd.	Picric acid found.
10 c.c.*	20.0 c.c.	20.4 c.c.	99.93%
15	12.6	9.5	99.4
15	20.0	15.85	99.6
25	25.0	14.05	99.7
25	30.0	21.5	99.5

* 10 c.c. contained 0.01712 g.

Estimation of Indigo.—Indigo has been estimated by titrating the sulphonated dyestuff, $C_{16}H_8N_2O_2(SO_3H)_2$, with vanadous sulphate in the presence sodium tartrate in an atmosphere of carbon dioxide.

Finely ground pure indigo, 1.624 g., (Kahlbaum, *pro analysi*) was mixed with 10 c.c. of concentrated sulphuric acid and heated in a water-bath at about 100° for an hour. The contents of the vessel were then cooled and dissolved in water and made up to 250 c.c. A known volume of this solution and about 50 c.c. (20%) of sodium tartrate solution were introduced into a conical flask fitted with a rubber stopper having three holes. Through one of these holes a current of carbon dioxide was introduced, another was fitted with a tube for the escape of the gas and a third was for adding the vanadous sulphate solution from the burette. This precaution was necessary to prevent the oxidation of indigo white by air.

TABLE V.

$$V^{++} \text{ soln.} = 0.5882 N/10.$$

$$1 \text{ C.c. of } 0.1 N V^{++} \text{ soln.} = \frac{C_{16}H_{10}N_2O_2}{2 \times 10^4} = 0.0131 \text{ g. of indigo.}$$

Indigo taken.	V-soln. reqd.	Indigo found.
10 c.c.*	8.4 c.c.	99.65%
10	8.35	99.06
20	16.70	99.06
25	20.90	99.15
25	20.90	99.15

* 10 c.c. contained 0.06496 g.

The solution was boiled and the hot solution titrated with V^{++} -solution until the blue colour of indigo disappeared.

Estimation of Methylene Blue.—Pure recrystallised methylene blue (2.3226 g.) free from zinc chloride was dissolved in water and the solution made up to 500 c.c. 50 C.c. of this solution was measured into a conical flask, a small quantity of hydrochloric acid was added, carbon dioxide was passed into the flask in the manner described for indigo, and the contents were heated to boiling. The hot solution was then titrated until the blue colour just disappeared.

TABLE VI.

$$V^{++}\text{-soln.} = 1.46 N/10.$$

$$1 \text{ C.c. of } 0.1N \text{ } V^{++} \text{ solution} = \frac{C_{12}H_{12}N_2SCl}{2 \times 10^4} = 0.015975 \text{ g. methylene blue.}$$

Methylene blue taken.	V-soln. reqd.	Methylene blue found.
50 c.c.*	9.90 c.c.	99.4%
50	9.95	99.91
50	9.90	99.4
50	9.85	98.91
50	9.90	99.4

* 50 c.c. contained 0.23226 g.

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